

Antifungal activity of Cubebin from *Piper cubeba*

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Abstract : The petrol and benzene extracts of the seeds of *Piper cubeba* yielded cubebin (1). The compound has been characterised on the basis of spectroscopic data and screened for antifungal activity.

Keywords : *Piper cubeba*, cubebin, antifungal activity.

Piper cubeba (Piperaceae), locally known as Kabab chini, is a climbing woody bush which grows in Java, Sumatra and Malay Archipelago. It is also cultivated to a small extent in Mysore state (India). It is used traditionally against a number of ailments such as throat infection, laryngitis, asthma, bronchitis, fever, pain in abdomen and genito-urinary disorders like cystitis, gonorrhoea, gleet and leucorrhoea etc¹. Previously isolated constituents of *Piper cubeba* include oxygenated cyclohexanes such as piperanol, piperanone² and lignans such as hinokinin, clusin cubebinone, butyrolactone, dihydrocubebin, dihydroclusin, cubebinin and dibenzylbutyrolactone³. We investigated the seeds of this plant to isolate active principles present in it and evaluate them for their antifungal activity.

Results and discussion

The seeds were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60–80) and benzene. Due to similar TLC behaviour of both the extracts, they were mixed and subjected to column chromatography. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate mixture afforded the lignan, cubebin (1)⁴. In the IR spectrum a broad band at 3418 cm⁻¹ indicated presence of a hydroxyl group. The other strong absorption bands at 1629 and 926 cm⁻¹ were due to carbon-carbon double bond and methylenedioxy functional groups. In ¹H NMR spectrum the aromatic region showed two multiplets integrating for six protons at δ 6.61–6.81. This indicated the presence of two benzene rings in the compound. A sharp singlet at δ 5.95 integrating for four protons was due to two methylenedioxy groups attached to different benzene rings. A fine triplet at δ 5.03 was assigned to C-2 proton. A multiplet which appeared at δ 3.81–3.86 was due to C-5 protons whereas a broad singlet (D₂O exchangeable) at δ 3.50 was assigned to hydroxylic

proton. The benzylic and methine protons (C-6, C-7, C-3, C-4 proton) were present in the form of multiplet at δ 1.80–2.66. The FAB mass spectrum showed M⁺ at m/z 356. The other significant peaks were present at m/z 338 (M⁺-H₂O), 203 and 135 (loss of fragments from peak at m/z 338).

The compound 1 was tested against four filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizoctonia bataticola*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium solani*) and a yeast *Candida albicans* using DMSO as solvent. Interestingly the compound demonstrated strong antifungal activity against *Rhizoctonia bataticola* and slightly less activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria alternata* and the yeast *Candida albicans* as compared to antifungal drug, nystatin. However, the antifungal activity of the compound against *Fusarium solani* was at par with nystatin. Inhibition zone size without and with antibiotic (100 unit/disc) are : *Rhizoctonia bataticola* 14, 13; *Fusarium solani* 18, 18; *Aspergillus niger* 17, 18 and *Alternaria alternata* 13, 17. The zone of growth inhibition of test fungi ranged from 13–18 mm at 100 μ g/disc of the test compound.

Experimental

The melting point was taken in open capillary tube and is uncorrected. The IR spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer RXI spectrometer using KBr, ^1H NMR spectrum on Bruker DRX-300 MHz in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ with TMS as internal standard and mass spectrum on Jeol Sx 102 (FAB). The purity of the compound was checked by TLC on aluminium sheet coated with silica gel-G (Merck, Germany) using benzene and ethyl acetate (3 : 1) as mobile phase and visualized by iodine vapors.

Extraction and isolation : Shade dried seeds of the *Piper cubeba* (5 kg) were grinded and successively extracted with petroleum ether and benzene. As the concentrated petroleum and benzene extracts showed similar TLC behaviour, they were mixed (30 g) and chromatographed over silica gel column. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) yielded **1** as a white crystalline solid (5 g). It was recrystallized from chloroform-petrol, m.p. 122–125 °C analyzed for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$; IR (KBr) ν_{mix} 3418 (OH), 1629 (C=C), 926 (methylenedioxy); ^1H NMR (300 MHz) δ 6.61–6.81 (6H, m), 5.95 (4H, s, O-CH₂-O), 5.03 (1H, t, C-2 proton), 3.81–3.86 (2H, m, -OCH₂), 3.35 (1H, brs, OH, D₂O exchangeable) and 1.82–2.27 (6H, m, benzylic and methine protons); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 103.2 (C-2), 53.0 (C-3), 45.7 (C-4), 72.5 (C-5), 39.1 (C-6), 38.7 (C-7), 100.7 (O-CH₂O), 132.2 (C-1"), 108.7 (C-2"), 147.9 (C-3"), 145.6 (C-4"), 109.1 (C-5"), 121.6 (C-6"), 133.8 (C-1'), 109.0 (C-2'), 147.2 (C-3'), 145.7 (C-4'), 109.0 (C-5'), 121.2 (C-6'); MS m/z (rel. int.) 356 (M⁺, 42), 339 (17), 209 (10), 203 (13), 136 (100), 135 (87), 122(8).

Antifungal activity : Sabouraud Dextrose (SD) (Hi-Media Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India) was used to culture test fungi. The filamentous fungi were grown at 28 °C for 3–5 days and then

appropriately diluted in sterile 0.8% saline solution to obtain an inoculum of viable spore/mycelial fragments of 10^5 CFU/ml. Similarly a cell suspension of 10^5 CFU/ml was prepared from *Candida albicans*, which was grown at 37 °C for 18 h⁵.

Antifungal activity of **1** was assayed by the disc diffusion method⁶ with little modification. Sterile paper disc impregnated with 100 μg of compound **1** and a disc without compound was used as a negative control. The inoculated plates were incubated for appropriate temperature and time as described above. The antifungal activity was evaluated by measuring the zone of growth inhibition of test organism around the disc. Antibiotic disc, nystatin was used as positive control.

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